

Addendum to IPDPS 2022 rebuttal (pap312): Summary of Previously Published Work on the Correlation between Temperature and Failures

This document is intended to supplement the text rebuttal for IPDPS paper pap312 in regard to current work investigating the correlation between temperature and failures.

There are roughly three categories of papers we see that consider the relationship between memory errors and temperature: (i) detailed longitudinal studies that find no correlation; (ii) hardware-focused analyses that show that DRAM operation changes with temperature (but device design can overcome these changes within normal operating ranges); and (iii) studies that don't have fine-grained temperature data but observe higher error rates on nodes that might further from the source of cold air. A summary of these work we are aware of are contained below. Given the details below, we believe this area of study is still unsettled and more data is necessary.

Bautista-Gomez et al. [1] found that there is not a strong correlation with temperature; most memory errors occur on servers running in a “nominal” temperature range. Similarly, Shroeder et al. [7] found that though temperature is known to strongly impact DIMM error rates in lab conditions, it has a surprisingly small effect on error behavior in the field, when taking all other factors into consideration. Any observed differences disappear when utilization is taken into account. El-Sayed et al. [2] show that though models for the effect of temperature on hardware components usually assume an exponential increase in failures as a function of temperature (based on the Arrhenius equation, roughly doubling failure rates for every 10-15C increase in temperature), they do not observe evidence for increasing rates of uncorrectable DRAM errors, DRAM DIMM replacements or node outages caused by DRAM problems as a function of temperature (within the range of temperature their data comprises. While no indication that hotter nodes have a higher probability of failing than colder nodes, they do believe that high variability in temperature seems to have a stronger effect on node reliability than average temperature. Lastly, Shin et al. [8] analyze power consumption, GPU failures logs and related environmental metrics of the Summit supercomputer located at Oak Ridge National Laboratory over the entire year of 2020. Using this data they show that overheating is not a significant aspect of GPU failures. In fact, for single- and double-bit errors, failures occurred at temperature significantly lower than average.

Liu et al. [4] show that For each 10 °C increase in device temperature, the DRAM cell retention time decreases by approximately 40% in the “common case”. Similarly, Kim et al. [3] show that although temperature reduces DRAM cell retention time, this reduction does not necessarily translate into more frequent failures.

Finally, Wang et al. [11] do not provide a detailed analysis of the relationship between failures and temperature but they observe that in some cases, top of rack systems experience more failures. Using motherboard sensors, the authors confirm that the temperature of top of rack systems is higher than the average. Similarly, Sridharan et al. [9] do not provide a detailed analysis of temperature, but they observe that temperature and SRAM faults are greater in chassis that are higher in the rack (and further from the floor where the cool air enters). Similarly, Nie et al. [5], Ostrouchov et al. [6] and Tiwari et al. [10] found that GPU reliability may depend on higher temperatures, but that dependence was weak and may correlate more strongly to utilization or be related to quality control issues.

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